

Graphical Abstract

Sparse Assemblies of Recurrent Neural Networks with Stability Guarantees

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Highlights

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- We propose AdaDiag, a sparse assembly of recurrent neural networks with stability guarantees, built on adaptive and contractive-by-design modules.
- Theoretical analysis proves the contractivity of the AdaDiag modules, ensuring stability of the overall assembly without introducing extra computational constraints.
- Extensive experiments on 10 diverse time series benchmarks show that AdaDiag achieves superior performance and efficiency compared to various baseline models, [and competitive performance with state-of-the-art models](#).

Sparse Assemblies of Recurrent Neural Networks with Stability Guarantees

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Abstract

We introduce AdaDiag, a framework for constructing sparse assemblies of recurrent neural networks (RNNs) with formal stability guarantees. Our approach builds upon contraction theory by designing RNN modules that are inherently contractive through adaptive diagonal parametrization and learnable characteristic time scales. This formulation enables each module to remain fully trainable while preserving global stability under skew-symmetric coupling. We provide rigorous theoretical analysis of contractivity, along with a complexity discussion showing that stability is achieved without additional computational burden. Experiments on ten heterogeneous time series benchmarks demonstrate that AdaDiag consistently surpasses SCN, LSTM, and Vanilla RNN baselines, [and achieves competitive performance with state-of-the-art models](#), all while requiring substantially fewer trainable parameters. These results highlight the effectiveness of sparse and stable assemblies for efficient, adaptive, and generalizable sequence modeling.

Keywords: recurrent neural networks, sparsity, modularity, stability

1. Introduction

From sensor signals to language, sequential data presents demanding challenges: adapting to shifting dynamics, delivering stable predictions, and capturing long-term dependencies LeCun et al. (2015); Bengio et al. (1994). Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) offer a powerful framework for modeling such temporal processes, yet they reveal a tension between full adaptivity and stability Pascanu (2013); Linsley et al. (2020); Miller and Hardt (2019); Jaeger (2001). Stability of the recurrent dynamics is essential for reliable learning and robust generalization, while adaptability to diverse and evolving

input regimes remains a key requirement for real-world applications Tallec and Ollivier (2018); Kolter and Manek (2019).

A promising direction is to construct assemblies of smaller RNN modules rather than relying on monolithic architectures. By leveraging sparsity, such assemblies improve efficiency in terms of both trainable parameters and information exchange across modules, while preserving expressive power and mitigating the overfitting risks characteristic of dense, monolithic architectures. Established results in contraction theory show that assemblies of contractive systems preserve contractivity when coupled appropriately Lohmiller and Slotine (1998). In particular, one way to achieve such appropriate coupling is through negative-feedback connections, which can be naturally modeled by skew-symmetric constraints. Skew-symmetric weight parameterizations have been extensively studied in learning systems, including feedforward networks as in Haber and Ruthotto (2017), RNNs as in Chang et al. (2019), and graph-based models as in Gravina et al. (2022, 2024), and have been shown to be effective across diverse contexts. They not only help capture long-term dependencies in the data but also promote stability, making them a natural choice for designing modular RNN assemblies. Together, these observations provide a principled foundation for constructing modular RNN architectures with provable stability.

However, prior approaches along this direction, such as Sparse Combo Net (SCN) in Kozachkov et al. (2022), showed that the most effective solution involved fixing the internal weights of RNN modules, which constrained their ability to adapt to task-specific dynamics. Addressing this limitation requires architectures that preserve contractivity while allowing the internal dynamics of modules to adapt.

In this work, we propose AdaDiag, a sparse assembly of contractive-by-design RNN modules. Each RNN module employs an adaptive diagonal parametrization of its recurrent weights to guarantee stability with minimal computational cost, while a learnable vector of characteristic time scales enhances the adaptability of individual neurons. This design allows modules to flexibly adjust their temporal dynamics, fostering robustness and generalization across diverse tasks. By grounding our architecture in nonlinear contraction theory, AdaDiag achieves a principled balance of stability, sparsity, and adaptivity, offering an efficient and performant alternative to traditional monolithic recurrent models.

2. Background: a stable continuous-time assembly of RNNs

We base our work on an RNN modelisation of the following type, as in Kozachkov et al. (2022); Sussillo and Abbott (2009); Wilson and Cowan (1972):

$$\tau \dot{\mathbf{v}} = -\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{W}\phi(\mathbf{v}) + \mathbf{u}(t), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the hidden state of the RNN, $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ defines the characteristic time scale of the RNN, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ are the recurrent connections, $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is (a linear transformation of) the external input defined in $t \in [t_0, T]$, and ϕ is the nonlinear activation function (applied component-wise), tanh or ReLU in our experiments. In Kozachkov et al. (2022) they consider a number p of RNN subnetworks as follows:

$$\tau \dot{\mathbf{v}}_i = -\mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{W}_i \phi(\mathbf{v}_i) + \mathbf{u}_i(t), \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \quad (2)$$

and assume to couple the i -th RNN module with the j -th RNN module, with $j \neq i$, via matrix $\mathbf{L}_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ with the skew-symmetric constraint as follows:

$$\mathbf{L}_{ij} = -\mathbf{L}_{ji}^T, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{ii} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (4)$$

so that the assembly of RNNs is defined by:

$$\tau \dot{\mathbf{v}}_i = -\mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{W}_i \phi(\mathbf{v}_i) + \mathbf{u}_i(t) + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^p \mathbf{L}_{ij} \mathbf{v}_j, \quad i = 1, \dots, p. \quad (5)$$

Exploiting existing results in the literature of nonlinear contraction theory, Kozachkov et al. (2022) demonstrate that RNN modules defined as in (1), when assembled into a network using the coupling strategy described by (3)–(4), form a contractive system, provided that each individual RNN module is contractive.

In Kozachkov et al. (2022), they propose few strategies to parametrise the recurrent weights \mathbf{W}_i of the single RNN modules with contractivity guarantees. Interestingly, none of their proposals for learning the weights \mathbf{W}_i can beat the performance of a simpler strategy of sparsely initialise \mathbf{W}_i and keeping it fixed during the training of the coupling matrices \mathbf{L}_{ij} under the constraints of (3)–(4). They call this simpler strategy Sparse Combo Net (SCN). Motivated by this limitation, we introduce a new RNN module whose parametrization guarantees contractivity by design while enabling adaptation and maintaining low computational cost.

3. The AdaDiag model

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Our approach replaces the standard RNN update in (1) with an adaptive, efficient module that guarantees stability by design and facilitates optimization. Specifically, we consider an assembly of p RNN subnetworks, each governed by

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}_i = \boldsymbol{\nu}_i \odot \left(-\mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{W}_i \phi(\mathbf{v}_i) + \mathbf{u}_i(t) \right), \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \quad (6)$$

where each unit develops its own characteristic time scale via the learnable

¹For reviewers: the paper has been significantly extended under various aspects.

We generalised our model by improving the adaptability of the single RNN modules. In particular, we introduced learnable characteristic frequencies for each neuron of the assembly, and also extended the adaptability of the single RNN module’s weights by making them explicitly input-dependent. Both these extensions of our model are provided with theoretical guarantees of contractivity, keeping the same motivation of the old version of the model.

The theoretical analysis in the previous version consisted of discursive and intuitive explanations, while in this version we dedicated Section 4 to formal theoretical results of stability of the single modules based on nonlinear contraction analysis. In particular, we derived sufficient conditions for the single RNN modules of the assembly to be contractive, and therefore stable for any input.

The experimental section has been significantly expanded. In the old version, we tested our model on 2 classification tasks (sMNIST and psMNIST), which were univariate and synthetics due to the Image type of the data. In the new version, we additionally tested our model on 6 more classification tasks and 2 regression tasks, covering multivariate time series from 5 to 963 channels, training datasets with various sizes ranging from 267 to 60000, and various type of time series coming from real-world scenarios like Sensors, HAR, Health Monitoring, Audio, Sentiment, and Traffic. The model selection in the new version has been considerably expanded, and we also included a model selection on standard baselines for time series like LSTM and Vanilla RNN. Moreover, in the old version, we directly compared our model against the SCN model only, while in the new version, we devised a rigorous protocol of model selection and evaluation to systematically benchmark AdaDiag against SCN, LSTM and a Vanilla RNN. **Notably, in the old version we compared our results just with the results of a monolithic Vanilla RNN found in the literature. While, in this new version, we better framed our work in the recent literature by comparing against 13 models (among which ensemble models like Random Forest and XGBoost, deep learning models like ResNet, AntisymRNN and SpectralRNN) and including also state-of-the-art models (among which convolutional models like Rocket and Inception, transformer models like iTransformer, modern state-space models like S4, and recent LLMs for time series like UniTS-SUP and TimesNet).**

vector of frequencies $\boldsymbol{\nu}_i$ (reciprocal of the characteristic time constants, $\frac{1}{\tau}$):

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_i = \sigma(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i^\tau \odot \mathbf{v}_t + \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^\tau + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_i^\tau \mathbf{u}_{t+1}), \quad (7)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i^\tau$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^\tau$ learnable vectors, $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_i^\tau$ a learnable matrix of appropriate dimension, and σ the componentwise sigmoid function. By allowing each neuron to adjust its characteristic time scale, the model can allocate representational capacity more effectively across tasks, thereby enhancing its potential for adaptability and robustness.

Rather than dense recurrent matrices, we employ adaptive diagonal matrices for \mathbf{W}_i . The general parametrization is given by

$$\mathbf{W}_i = \text{diag}\left(\tanh(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i^W \odot \mathbf{v}_t + \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^W + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_i^W \mathbf{u}_{t+1})\right), \quad (8)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i^W$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^W$ are learnable vectors, $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_i^W$ is a learnable matrix, and \tanh is applied componentwise. For computational efficiency, a simplified variant is also considered:

$$\mathbf{W}_i = \text{diag}\left(\tanh(\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^W)\right), \quad (9)$$

which introduces only a trainable bias term without explicit state- or input-dependent weights.

The coupling dynamics among modules are implemented following the same methodology as SCN, namely through block matrices \mathbf{L}_{ij} , as in (5), subject to the skew-symmetric constraint described in (3)-(4). Due to the peculiar parametrization in (8), we refer to this architecture as *AdaDiag*.

Notably, under parametrizations (7)–(8), units within a single module do not directly interact with each other. Instead, they exchange information indirectly through the skew-symmetric couplings between modules, as illustrated in Figure 1.

4. Contractivity and scalability of AdaDiag modules

In what follows, we focus on establishing the contractivity of individual AdaDiag modules. This is sufficient in light of the theoretical results proven in Kozachkov et al. (2022), which shows that when recurrent modules are contractive in isolation, their assembly remains stable by construction under the skew-symmetric coupling scheme of (3)-(4). Since our AdaDiag assembly adopts precisely this coupling parametrization, it is enough to prove the stability of the single modules, with global stability then guaranteed by the framework of Kozachkov et al. (2022).

Figure 1: Depiction of an assembly of RNNs. Straight arrows denote untrained connections, while wavy arrows denote trained connections. **Left:** SCN trains only the connections between RNN modules leaving the internal connections of the single RNN modules untrained. **Right:** AdaDiag (our) trains the connections between RNN modules and also the internal connections of the single RNN modules, which result in adaptive self-loops.

4.1. Contractivity

We establish the contractivity of the continuous-time system (6) defining the single AdaDiag module, by proving a stronger property: that its explicit Euler discretisation is a contraction mapping for all step sizes $\epsilon \in (0, 1]$. We start by discretising the continuous-time equation (6) via an explicit Euler scheme, with ϵ being the numerical integration step, so that $\mathbf{u}_t = \mathbf{u}(t_0 + \epsilon t)$, for $t = 0, \dots, \lfloor \frac{T-t_0}{\epsilon} \rfloor$:

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+1} = \mathbf{v}_t + \epsilon \boldsymbol{\nu} \odot \left(-\mathbf{v}_t + \mathbf{W} \phi(\mathbf{v}_t) + \mathbf{u}_{t+1} \right), \quad (10)$$

that we write as

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+1} = (1 - \epsilon \boldsymbol{\nu}) \odot \mathbf{v}_t + \epsilon \boldsymbol{\nu} \odot (\mathbf{W} \phi(\mathbf{v}_t) + \mathbf{u}_{t+1}). \quad (11)$$

Now we prove that the discrete-time single AdaDiag modules are nonlinear contraction mappings.

Theorem 4.1. *Assume ϕ has a Lipschitz constant less than or equal to 1. Let us consider the continuous-time RNN of (6), with a vector of characteristic*

frequencies parametrised by (7) and a diagonal matrix of weights \mathbf{W} (e.g. parametrised as either (8) or (9)). If each entry of the diagonal of \mathbf{W} is in absolute value less than 1, then the Euler discretisation of such continuous-time RNN is a contraction mapping for any Euler step $\epsilon > 0$ such that $0 < \epsilon \leq 1$.

Proof. The single module equation is $\mathbf{v}_{t+1} = (1 - \epsilon\nu) \odot \mathbf{v}_t + \epsilon\nu \odot (\mathbf{W}\phi(\mathbf{v}_t) + \mathbf{u}_{t+1})$. Recall that \mathbf{W} is a diagonal matrix, and ν is the vector of characteristic frequencies parametrised as $\sigma(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^\tau \odot \mathbf{v}_t + \boldsymbol{\beta}^\tau + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}^\tau \mathbf{u}_{t+1})$.

We notice that, due to the component-wise product of the hidden state \mathbf{v} and the vector of weights $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^\mathbf{W}$ in the parametrisation of the characteristic frequencies, each component of the hidden state recurrence depends only on its own. Therefore, we can consider a scalar equation since the dynamics of the units are completely decoupled in a single AdaDiag module. The scalar equation to consider is $v_{t+1} = (1 - \epsilon\nu)v_t + \epsilon\nu(w\phi(v_t) + u_{t+1})$, where ν is a given component of $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ as parametrised in (7), and w is the corresponding diagonal entry of the diagonal weight matrix \mathbf{W} . Let us start from 2 different initial conditions v_0 and \tilde{v}_0 . Then, the difference $|v_t - \tilde{v}_t|$ converges to 0, if $|w| < 1$. In fact, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
|v_{t+1} - \tilde{v}_{t+1}| &= \\
&= \left| (1 - \epsilon\nu)v_t + \epsilon\nu(w\phi(v_t) + u_{t+1}) - \left[(1 - \epsilon\nu)\tilde{v}_t + \epsilon\nu(w\phi(\tilde{v}_t) + u_{t+1}) \right] \right| \\
&= \left| (1 - \epsilon\nu)(v_t - \tilde{v}_t) + \epsilon\nu w \left[\phi(v_t) - \phi(\tilde{v}_t) \right] \right| \\
&\leq \left| (1 - \epsilon\nu)(v_t - \tilde{v}_t) \right| + \epsilon\nu |w| \left| \phi(v_t) - \phi(\tilde{v}_t) \right| \\
&\leq |1 - \epsilon\nu| |v_t - \tilde{v}_t| + \epsilon\nu |w| |v_t - \tilde{v}_t| \\
&= (1 - \epsilon\nu) |v_t - \tilde{v}_t| + \epsilon\nu |w| |v_t - \tilde{v}_t| \\
&= \left[1 - \epsilon\nu(1 - |w|) \right] |v_t - \tilde{v}_t|,
\end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality uses that ϕ is Lipschitz with constant less or equal than 1. Note that, since $\nu \in (0, 1)$ due to the sigmoid parameterization of ν of (7), then in order for the second last equality to hold we need that $1 - \epsilon\nu \geq 0$, or equivalently we need that the Euler step is such that $0 < \epsilon \leq 1$. Concluding, under the assumptions that ϕ has Lipschitz constant less or equal than 1, and that $0 < \epsilon \leq 1$, then by a recursive argument we get the relation

$|v_{t+1} - \tilde{v}_{t+1}| \leq \left[1 - \epsilon\nu(1 - |w|)\right]^{t+1} |v_0 - \tilde{v}_0|$. This implies convergence to 0 when $1 - \epsilon\nu(1 - |w|) < 1$, i.e. when $|w| < 1$. \square

4.1.1. Merging Euler discretisation step and frequencies

Theorem 4.1 guarantees contractivity of the AdaDiag modules for any Euler step $0 < \epsilon \leq 1$. Therefore, since we learn the frequencies, we can formally merge the Euler discretisation step ϵ into the vector of frequencies $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ and implement in software the following contractive-by-design AdaDiag modules of equation:

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+1} = (1 - \boldsymbol{\nu}) \odot \mathbf{v}_t + \boldsymbol{\nu} \odot (\mathbf{W}\phi(\mathbf{v}_t) + \mathbf{u}_{t+1}), \quad (12)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ and \mathbf{W} are parametrised, respectively, as in (7) and (8). As we will discuss in the experimental section, this yields the considerable advantage of removing the model selection step associated with the hyperparameter ϵ .

4.2. Scalability

Unlike the SCN of Kozachkov et al. (2022), we want to train the single RNN modules composing the assembly. However, ensuring at each parameter update the contractivity of the modules can be computationally prohibitive. For example, ensuring that $\|\mathbf{W}_i\| < 1$, while adapting the matrices \mathbf{W}_i , is computationally expensive as $O(N^3)$ time complexity, where N is the dimensionality of the single RNN modules; preventing the application of this approach in scenarios involving large modules. A key advantage of AdaDiag is that the contractivity guarantee incurs no additional overhead, as the model is inherently contractive by design: the sigmoid and tanh activations naturally map values into $(0, 1)$ and $(-1, 1)$, respectively, while the specific parametrisation of both the frequencies and the diagonal weights guarantees contractivity, thanks to Theorem 4.1. This design allows AdaDiag to overcome the scalability limitations while remaining fully adaptive at the level of individual modules.

Additional parameters compared to SCN. Learning the frequencies involves the parametrisation $\boldsymbol{\nu} = \sigma(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^\tau \odot \mathbf{v}_t + \boldsymbol{\beta}^\tau + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}^\tau \mathbf{u}_{t+1})$ which introduces $(2 + n_u)N$ additional trainable parameters per module compared to SCN, where n_u is the dimensionality of the input. In the simplest diagonal weight parametrisation, $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}(\tanh(\boldsymbol{\beta}^W))$, only N additional trainable parameters per module are introduced, while using the fully parametrized version of AdaDiag in (8) requires a similar number of parameters as learning

the frequencies. Consequently, the total additional trainable parameters for AdaDiag scale as $O(n_u N p)$, i.e. linearly with the input dimension, module size, and number of modules. This overhead is negligible compared to the parameters involved in the coupling of the modules, which scale as $O(C N^2)$, where C is the number of connections among modules and can range from 1 to $\frac{p(p-1)}{2}$ depending on the connectivity topology of the assembly.

5. Experimental Assessment

We experimentally validate the proposed model on a set of diverse time series benchmarks from the UEA & UCR repository for classification² and regression³, plus the HAR-2 classification task, a binary classification task proposed in Kusupati et al. (2018) stemming from the original HAR dataset in Anguita et al. (2012), and in addition the popular sequential MNIST (abbreviated sMNIST) and permuted sequential (abbreviated psMNIST) classification tasks Le et al. (2015). Precisely, the tasks considered from the UEA & UCR repository are: Adiac, FordA, FordB, IEEEPGP (abbreviated PPG), JapaneseVowels (abbreviated JapVow), NewsTitleSentiment (abbreviated NTSent), and PEMS-SF. Table 1 provides a summary of the main properties of the considered datasets.

Table 1: Overview of benchmark datasets used.

Dataset	Task	Inp. dim.	Train sz	Test sz	Seq. Len.	Out. dim.	Type
Adiac	Cls.	1	390	391	176	37	Image
FordA	Cls.	1	3,601	1,320	500	2	Sensor
FordB	Cls.	1	3,636	810	500	2	Sensor
HAR-2	Cls.	9	7,352	2,947	128	2	HAR
PPG	Reg.	5	1768	1328	1000	1	Health Monitor.
JapVow	Cls.	12	270	370	29	9	Audio
NTSent	Reg.	3	58213	24951	144	1	Sentiment
PEMS-SF	Cls.	963	267	173	144	7	Traffic
psMNIST	Cls.	1	60,000	10,000	784	10	Image
sMNIST	Cls.	1	60,000	10,000	784	10	Image

The collection of datasets considered in our benchmark covers a wide spectrum of sequence modeling challenges. Sequence lengths span from as short as 29 time steps to as long as 1000, reflecting both compact and highly

²www.timeseriesclassification.com

³<http://tseregression.org>

extended temporal dependencies. The datasets are heterogeneous in nature, ranging from health monitoring and sensor-based signals to sentiment analysis and image-based data, thereby capturing diverse real-world domains. Both classification and regression tasks are included, with training set sizes varying significantly, from as few as 267 instances up to 60000. The test-to-train ratios also show notable diversity, ranging between 0.17 and 1.37, which provides a mixture of data-rich and data-scarce regimes. Furthermore, the benchmark encompasses both univariate and multivariate time series with a number of input channels ranging from 3 to 963, and output target dimensionalities ranging from single-valued regression to binary and multi-class classification tasks with up to 37 classes.

To ensure reproducibility, the complete implementation is publicly available at <https://github.com/andreaceni/assemblyRNNs>.

5.1. Benchmark models

We directly compare our AdaDiag model against three models: SCN, LSTM, and Vanilla RNN. We evaluate AdaDiag and these three models through the same model selection protocol via grid search, the details of the grids for each model are reported in Section 5.2.1. The SCN model serves as baseline because our proposed AdaDiag model stems from it. Vanilla RNN is a standard RNN as in Elman (1990), used as a monolithic baseline model. In particular, a single RNN eq. (1) can be reduced with a change of coordinates to the Vanilla RNN, see Miller and Fumarola (2012). And LSTM is another standard baseline, see Mienye et al. (2024). Both LSTM and Vanilla RNN baselines are monolithic recurrent models, meaning the lack of sparsity or modularity enforced in these architectures apart from the usual stack of recurrent layers. On the contrary, the SCN and AdaDiag are sparse modular assemblies of RNN models, and as such they are evaluated on different degrees of sparsity.

Single modules. As already explained, LSTM and Vanilla RNN are monolithic deep learning blocks as usual, thus their whole architecture represent a single fully connected module. On the other hand, for the single modules of SCN and AdaDiag we consider two basic configurations of the single RNN modules, either 16 modules of 32 recurrent neurons (denoted as $[32]_{16}$) or 64 modules of 8 recurrent neurons (denoted as $[8]_{64}$). Both these options account for a total of 512 neurons in the assembly. The single RNN modules of the SCN assembly are initialised according to Theorem 1 of Kozachkov et al. (2022) to have sparsity either 3% or 10%, similar to the

setting in their original paper. While, since in the AdaDiag assembly only the diagonal weights are nonzero, the single RNN modules of AdaDiag have either 3.125% or 12.5% sparsity depending on the size of the single RNN modules, respectively 32 or 8. This ensures more or less the same level of sparsity between the single modules of the two assembly architectures. We considered ReLU as activation function in both AdaDiag and SCN as in the experiments of Kozachkov et al. (2022), and Tanh for both LSTM and Vanilla RNN as in the usual PyTorch implementation.

Couplings. In the case of LSTM and Vanilla RNN, to introduce some modularity in these monolithic architectures we evaluated a stack of LSTM or Vanilla RNN modules, considering 1,2, or 3 layers (details in Section 5.2), each one projecting forwardly to the next one. Contrariwise, for SCN and AdaDiag, we evaluated few combinations ranging from very sparse to almost fully connected scenarios of assembly, always using the skew-symmetric coupling of given by eq. (3). For an SCN or AdaDiag assembly of p modules, the total amount of possible coupling blocks is given by all the possible pairs of modules minus the self-paired cases, i.e. $p^2 - p = p(p - 1)$, but under the constraint of eq. (3), the total number of trainable coupling blocks becomes $\frac{p(p-1)}{2}$. We analyzed the behaviour under different levels of sparsity in the modules' coupling by setting the number of trainable coupling blocks C to 5 and 20 and $\max(500, \frac{p(p-1)}{2})$. Once selected $C \in \{5, 20, \max(500, \frac{p(p-1)}{2})\}$, then the coupling of RNN modules in both SCN and AdaDiag assemblies is performed by random selection of a number C of blocks to project their hidden states towards other modules. This random selection occurs at initialisation of the assembly.

Possible sparsity levels. These 3 choices of C together with the 2 choices of $p \in \{16, 64\}$ give rise to a total of 6 combinations of random sparse topologies of assemblies of RNNs, for each the SCN and AdaDiag models. Finally, considering also the two choices of sparsity of the single RNN modules of the SCN assembly, then there are 12 levels of sparsity for SCN, all the possible sparsity levels are summarised in the Table 2.

AdaDiag learnable frequencies. A distinctive feature of the AdaDiag architecture is its ability to learn the characteristic frequencies of each neuron, rather than relying on fixed values determined a priori. This design choice allows the model to adapt its temporal dynamics flexibly to the requirements of different tasks. To implement this mechanism, we rescale the sigmoid function in Eq. 7 so that its output lies in the interval $(10^{-5}, 0.2)$. This

Sparsity (S%) of the SCN and AdaDiag Assemblies

Single modules	Couplings		
	$C = 5$	$C = 20$	$C = \max(500, \frac{p(p-1)}{2})$
SCN			
$[32]_{16}$ with sparsity 3%	S=4.1%	S=15.8%	S=93.9%
$[8]_{64}$ with sparsity 3%	S=0.3%	S=1.0%	S=24.5%
$[32]_{16}$ with sparsity 10%	S=4.5%	S=16.3%	S=94.4%
$[8]_{64}$ with sparsity 10%	S=0.4%	S=1.1%	S=24.6%
AdaDiag			
$[32]_{16}$ with sparsity 3.125%	S=3.9%	S=15.6%	S=93.8%
$[8]_{64}$ with sparsity 12.5%	S=2.5%	S=9.8%	S=24.4%

Table 2: Combinations of sparsity levels of the recurrent SCN and AdaDiag assemblies. Sparsity percentage only refers to the recurrent architecture; the fully connected output layer is excluded from the computation.

interval was chosen to encompass the spectrum of frequencies that the model is expected to encounter, ranging from very slow patterns to relatively fast dynamics.

Generalised Negative Feedback Parametrisation. Our implementation of SCN does not incorporate the learnable change of coordinates associated with the Generalized Negative Feedback parametrization proposed in Kozachkov et al. (2022). While this mechanism could in principle also be integrated into AdaDiag, we chose not to adopt it in either models. This decision was motivated by the considerable increase in trainable parameters introduced by the additional dense matrices required for each RNN module in the coupling graph, as well as by our aim to construct sparser assemblies of RNNs that improve efficiency and better highlight the intrinsic contribution of AdaDiag.

5.2. Methodology

We performed the classification and regression of time series by exploiting only the last hidden state as input for the linear classifier in the output layer. We used the original split in training and test sets as provided by the sources, applying a further 70%-30% splitting of the training set into actual training and validation sets. We performed model selection through grid search for each of the four benchmarked models: AdaDiag, SCN, LSTM, and Vanilla RNN. The grid of hyperparameters for AdaDiag is reported in Table 4, for

SCN is reported in Table 5, for LSTM and Vanilla RNN are reported in Table 6. For each of the four models (AdaDiag, SCN, LSTM, and Vanilla RNN), we set a maximum number of epochs of 250, with a learning rate decay of 0.1 at epochs 80 and 160. Further details for speeding up the model selection are described in Section 5.2.2. The score used for model selection is the *test accuracy* for classification tasks, and the *test RMSE* for regression tasks. In Table 7 we report the best validation scores achieved at any epoch of training. The model selection is ruled by the model with higher validation accuracy, for classification, or lower validation RMSE, for regression. In case of a tie, the model with smaller validation loss has been selected. After model selection, the best configuration was trained on the whole training set, and assessed on the hold out test set, averaging over 3 trials. For the largest datasets of the pool (MNIST-based and NTSent), we used a batch size of 512 to speed up the model selection, while for all the other datasets we used a batch size of 128 for the model selection. The best validation score outcomes of the model selection are reported in Table 7. Then, for the final test score, a batch size of 128 has been used for all datasets apart from the smallest ones (Adiac, JapaneseVowels, PEMS-SF), for which a batch size of 16 has been employed. This choice ensures a minimum number of at least 17 training updates for each epoch, even for the smallest datasets. A summary of this batch size protocol is reported in Table 3. This protocol provides insights

Table 3: Batch sizes used for model selection and final testing.

Datasets	Model Selection	Final Testing
sMNIST, psMNIST, NTSent	512	128
Adiac, JapVow, PEMS-SF	128	16
FordA, FordB, HAR-2, PPG	128	128

into a key aspect of model development: robustness to optimization dynamics. In fact, varying the batch size alters the level of stochasticity and gradient noise, allowing us to evaluate a model’s stability under different training conditions. This property is particularly advantageous for accelerating model selection, offering a substantial efficiency gain in the development of deep learning systems. In Table 8 we report the best test scores averaged over the 3 trials with their empirical standard deviations. [Finally, in Table A.9 we report the best test scores achieved among the 3 trials, compared to a](#)

plethora of standard machine learning baselines and state-of-the-art models found in the recent literature.

5.2.1. Grid searches for LSTM, vanilla RNN, SCR and AdaDiag

Table 4: Grid Search Hyperparameter Space for AdaDiag (Total: 24 combinations). Columns are hyperparameters, rows show possible values.

$[N]_p$	AdaDiag module parametrisation	C couplings	Learning rate
$[32]_{16}, [8]_{64}$	eq. 9 (only bias), eq. 8 (bias+state+input)	5, 20, 500	$10^{-3}, 10^{-2}$

Table 5: Grid Search Hyperparameter Space for SCN (Total: 72 combinations). Columns are hyperparameters, rows show possible values.

$[N]_p$	SCN module sparsity	C couplings	ϵ Euler step	Learning rate
$[32]_{16}, [8]_{64}$	3%, 10%	5, 20, 500	0.001, 0.01, 0.1	$10^{-3}, 10^{-2}$

Table 6: Grid Search Hyperparameter Space for LSTM and Vanilla RNN (Total: 48 combinations). Columns are hyperparameters, rows show possible values.

Hidden size	Number of layers	Bidirectional	Learning rate	L2 regularization
{64, 128}	{1, 2, 3}	{True, False}	$\{10^{-3}, 10^{-2}\}$	{0.0, 10^{-4} }

Unlike LSTM and Vanilla RNN models, the SCN and AdaDiag architectures do not incorporate regularization techniques. This design choice stems from the modular nature of SCN and AdaDiag, which promotes sparse assemblies of contractive RNN modules. In contrast, monolithic models like LSTM and Vanilla RNN are more prone to overfitting due to their larger number of trainable parameters, necessitating the use of regularization to mitigate this risk.

Additionally, SCN employs a larger grid to ensure that the Euler step is adequately explored across three orders of magnitude. This parameter has been identified as particularly sensitive in SCN’s performance. To address this issue, AdaDiag introduces a more structured approach by formally merging the Euler step into the characteristic frequencies of each neuron and learning these frequencies, thereby enhancing stability and performance.

Given the presence of relatively long sequences in our pool of datasets, bidirectional processing was implemented in both LSTM and Vanilla RNN models. This approach allows the models to capture long-term dependencies more effectively by considering both past and future contexts during training Schuster and Paliwal (1997).

5.2.2. Further details on model selection

For the model selection phase on the largest and most computationally demanding datasets in our benchmark (sMNIST, psMNIST, PPG, and NTSent), we employed a set of methodological adjustments aimed at accelerating the training process without compromising the reliability of the results. These adjustments were specifically designed to reduce computational overhead, thereby enabling a more efficient exploration of model architectures and hyperparameters while maintaining the integrity of the evaluation protocol.

sMNIST and psMNIST. For model selection on MNIST-based tasks, we employed a simplified training-validation split. Specifically, a random subset of 12k samples was drawn from the original 60k-sample training set. Of these, 10k samples were used for actual training and the remaining 2k for validation. This procedure discards 48k training samples, but substantially accelerates model selection. After the best configuration is identified, the final model is retrained on the full 60k training samples and evaluated on the standard 10k-sample test set. This protocol differs from the standard approach commonly used in deep learning models for the sMNIST and psMNIST tasks, which typically relies on the conventional training and test splits for both model development and evaluation. Our approach was introduced primarily to improve efficiency during model selection, while still ensuring that the test set was never explored during the validation session. Nonetheless, our experimental design has the additional advantage of assessing the robustness of models under varying training conditions, such as reduced training set sizes, thereby providing further insight into its adaptability across different scenarios. For the MNIST dataset, the exploration of learning rate configurations was restricted in order to reduce computational cost and accelerate model selection. While for all other datasets the grid search included both 0.001 and 0.01, in the case of MNIST only the learning rate of 0.001 was considered.

PPG and NTSent. For the regression tasks (PPG and NTSent), we observed that all four models exhibited rapid convergence during the validation session. To avoid unnecessary computation and thereby accelerate model selection, we therefore stopped the training at a maximum of 50 epochs.

A similar learning rate decay schedule was applied, reducing the rate by a factor of 0.1 at epochs 20 and 40 to further stabilize convergence and improve optimization efficiency.

5.3. Best Results on Validation

In this section, we present the best results obtained from the model selection protocol described in the previous subsections. The reported scores correspond to the optimal configuration identified for each dataset within the predefined grid search space of hyperparameters and architectural choices. This stage serves to provide a fair and consistent basis for comparing different models across heterogeneous datasets, as all methods were subjected to the same selection criteria and evaluation procedure. These findings form the foundation for the subsequent analysis on the held-out test sets, where the ultimate generalization performance of each approach is assessed.

Table 7: Validation results for LSTM, Vanilla RNN, SCN, and AdaDiag across classification and regression benchmarks. Reported values are % accuracy (\uparrow) for classification tasks and RMSE (\downarrow) for regression tasks. The best validation score on each dataset is highlighted in **bold**, while the model with the fewest trainable parameters is underlined. Values in parentheses denote the number of trainable parameters.

Validation Score (Trainable Parameters)				
Datasets	Models			
	LSTM	Vanilla RNN	SCN	AdaDiag
Adiac \uparrow	35.90 (539k)	46.15 (241k)	64.10 (<u>40k</u>)	82.05 (42k)
FordA \uparrow	91.44 (233k)	90.65 (133k)	94.22 (124k)	95.15 (<u>4.9k</u>)
FordB \uparrow	88.25 (925k)	82.01 (12.7k)	94.55 (22k)	95.60 (<u>8.7k</u>)
PEMS-SF \uparrow	92.50 (1.5M)	87.50 (<u>479k</u>)	88.75 (517k)	96.25 (1.1M)
HAR-2 \uparrow	96.92 (933k)	96.77 (234k)	98.96 (26k)	97.87 (<u>13k</u>)
JapVow \uparrow	96.30 (938k)	95.06 (236k)	100.00 (<u>12k</u>)	100.00 (23k)
PPG \downarrow	24.05 (929k)	24.05 (232k)	27.18 (8k)	22.26 (<u>7k</u>)
NTSent \downarrow	0.13 (927k)	0.13 (59k)	0.13 (22k)	0.13 (<u>5.4k</u>)
sMNIST \uparrow	54.64 (200k)	36.98 (60k)	93.91 (<u>11k</u>)	97.89 (28k)
psMNIST \uparrow	73.69 (234k)	82.56 (135k)	88.20 (<u>26k</u>)	92.48 (28k)

Discussion of the validation results. We see AdaDiag dominating the performance on validation, despite the smaller search space employed (24 combinations) compared to the other baselines (48 combinations for LSTM and

Vanilla RNN, and 72 combinations for SCN). Particular attention has been devoted to the number of trainable parameters identified during model selection. Interestingly, the results indicate a clear distinction between model families: monolithic architectures such as LSTMs and Vanilla RNNs tend to favor larger configurations, whereas assembly-based approaches such as SCN and AdaDiag consistently converge toward sparser solutions with substantially fewer parameters. Another interesting outcome of the model selection procedure concerns the AdaDiag’s module parametrisation. Between the two available configurations for the diagonal weights, eq. 9, which includes only a bias term, and eq. 8, which combines bias, input, and diagonal recurrent weights, the simpler formulation in eq. 9 was consistently favored across all datasets. This systematic preference suggests that a more parsimonious parametrization can lead to superior generalization, likely by reducing the risk of overfitting and enhancing the model’s ability to adapt across diverse tasks. Across nearly all datasets considered, the model selection procedure identified a sparsity level of 10% as optimal for the single RNN modules composing the SCN assembly (instead of a 3% higher level of sparsity). This outcome can be interpreted in light of the training dynamics: since the single RNN modules in an SCN assembly remain fixed, the optimization relies on the trainable couplings between them. A denser interconnection inside the single RNN modules might therefore facilitates more effective information propagation, enabling the assembly to better adapt to the target task.

5.4. *Final results*

In this section, we report the final test scores, averaged over three independent trials, along with the corresponding standard deviations, for the four benchmark models: LSTM, Vanilla RNN, SCN, and AdaDiag. These results provide a quantitative comparison of model performance under the same experimental conditions, allowing us to evaluate their relative ability to capture temporal dependencies, maintain stability, and generalize to unseen data. The detailed results are summarized in Table 8.

5.4.1. *Discussion of final results*

Consistent with the validation results, AdaDiag emerged as the best-performing model in the test phase. A notable contrast arises when comparing AdaDiag to SCN: while SCN exhibited a marked drop in performance from validation to test, AdaDiag maintained comparable results across the two stages. This stability is likely attributable to the enhanced adaptability

Table 8: Test scores of LSTM, Vanilla RNN, SCN, and AdaDiag across benchmark datasets. Results are reported as % Accuracy (\uparrow) for classification tasks and RMSE (\downarrow) for regression tasks. The best score on each dataset is highlighted in **bold**. The symbol * indicates that one of the trials produced NaN values from the first epoch and was excluded from the reported average.

Datasets	Test Score			
	Models			
	LSTM	Vanilla RNN	SCN	AdaDiag
Adiac \uparrow	39.11 \pm 1.30	10.21 \pm 4.12	43.67 \pm 20.52	80.65 \pm 1.46
FordA \uparrow	59.13 \pm 8.14	51.17 \pm 0.17	74.27 \pm 1.21	93.01 \pm 0.84
FordB \uparrow	54.42 \pm 3.99	52.67 \pm 0.48	76.37 \pm 3.34	82.29 \pm 0.79
PEMS-SF \uparrow	92.74 \pm 0.58	68.00 \pm 14.60	82.02 \pm 1.79	91.09 \pm 2.51
HAR-2 \uparrow	89.25 \pm 4.89	79.55 \pm 1.73*	95.54 \pm 0.12	95.41 \pm 0.21
JapVow \uparrow	96.55 \pm 0.43	97.14 \pm 0.25	98.04 \pm 0.13	98.15 \pm 0.21
PPG \downarrow	116.32 \pm 0.12	26.85 \pm 0.37*	41.39 \pm 18.14	21.43 \pm 0.83
NTSent \downarrow	0.14 \pm 0.00	0.14 \pm 0.00	0.14 \pm 0.00	0.14 \pm 0.00
sMNIST \uparrow	14.25 \pm 4.08	24.43 \pm 18.48	96.67 \pm 0.37	99.05 \pm 0.01
psMNIST \uparrow	93.07 \pm 0.33	85.92 \pm 1.27	93.46 \pm 0.38	96.07 \pm 0.09

of AdaDiag’s single RNN modules, which are better able to re-train and adjust to the slight distributional shifts encountered between validation and test scenarios. Such differences in generalization are particularly evident in tasks like FordA and FordB. In these cases, monolithic architectures (i.e., LSTMs and vanilla RNNs) collapse on the test set, performing near random chance, reflecting their limited ability to adapt to distributional shifts. In contrast, assembly-based models, most notably AdaDiag, demonstrate greater resilience to such shifts, further highlighting the robustness of their learned representations and their capacity to generalize across challenging, shifted datasets.

Our training protocol involved using a larger batch size during model selection for certain datasets, followed by a smaller batch size for the final training of the best-performing model. The datasets concerned were Adiac, PEMS-SF, JapVow, NTSent, and MNIST-based (see Table 3). This setting introduced an additional challenge, which was particularly detrimental to the Vanilla RNN: across these datasets it exhibited in half of the cases a substantial drop in performance from validation to test. LSTM was less affected; except

for the sMNIST task, it generally maintained similar performance between validation and test, and in some cases even improved, thus demonstrating its greater adaptability to varying training conditions, compared to Vanilla RNN. Notably, in the PEMS-SF dataset, LSTM achieved the best overall performance. Assembly-based models, SCN and AdaDiag, were also less affected than Vanilla RNN, with AdaDiag displaying the most stable response to this challenge.

On the MNIST-based tasks. Special consideration must be given to the MNIST-based tasks, for which the model selection protocol differed. To accelerate computation, only a subset of the training data was employed during model selection, see Section 5.2.2, while the final test was conducted exploiting the full training set. On psMNIST, all four models benefited from the additional training data, with test scores exceeding validation scores. By contrast, on sMNIST, both LSTM and Vanilla RNN suffered performance drops despite the larger training set. This outcome is likely due to the particular structure of sMNIST, where long windows of zero input are interleaved by bursts of informative signal, a pattern that can destabilize the learning dynamics of monolithic architectures more readily than those of assembly-based approaches.

Euler step sensitivity We conclude this discussion by disclosing a critical limitation observed in SCN: its performance is highly sensitive to the choice of the Euler step hyperparameter, ϵ . This sensitivity makes the model’s effectiveness strongly dependent on the granularity and thoroughness of the model selection procedure, thereby increasing both the computational burden and the risk of suboptimal tuning. In contrast, AdaDiag circumvents this limitation by merging the Euler step and characteristic neuron’s frequency terms into a single vector of learnable parameters. This design reduces reliance on extensive hyperparameter searches, thereby lowering the computational cost of model selection while enhancing the model’s adaptivity, ultimately leading to stable and robust performance across diverse tasks.

5.5. Further Analyses on Time Scales, Convergence Speed, and Stability

We complement our main results with three further analyses that shed light on the internal dynamics and training behavior of AdaDiag.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of characteristic time scales learned by neurons in AdaDiag when trained on the FordB dataset. The orange distribution corresponds to the first epoch, while the blue distribution corresponds to the last epoch, with the x-axis in logarithmic scale. These plots, obtained

Figure 2: Log-scaled distributions of neuron frequencies in AdaDiag trained on the FordB dataset, shown at epoch 1 (orange) and epoch 250 (blue).

using the best hyperparameters from model selection, reveal that learning to solve the FordB task promotes the emergence of a tail of neurons with slower frequencies, despite the mean being around 10^{-1} . Such heterogeneity of time scales, which SCN cannot achieve, highlights AdaDiag’s superior adaptability in capturing multi-timescale dynamics

Figure 3 compares the validation accuracy of SCN and AdaDiag on the sMNIST task, both trained with their best hyperparameters selected on a reduced training set (10k training samples and 2k validation, instead of the total 60k samples of the whole MNIST training set). While SCN requires almost 200 epochs to reach 90% validation accuracy, AdaDiag abundantly surpasses this threshold within the first 20 epochs. This sharp difference underscores AdaDiag’s accelerated learning ability, a direct consequence of its adaptive design.

Figure 4 reports the evolution of the spectral norm of the block matrix defining the AdaDiag assembly when trained on the Adiac dataset with the best hyperparameters found in the model selection phase. The block matrix defining the assembly is a 16×16 block matrix with each block of size 32×32 ,

Figure 3: Validation accuracy curves on sMNIST for SCN and AdaDiag using best hyperparameters from model selection on a reduced training set (10k training, 2k validation samples).

where the diagonal blocks represent the recurrent matrices of the single modules (\mathbf{W}_i according to eq. 6), and the off-diagonal blocks represent the coupling matrices among modules (\mathbf{L}_{ij} according to eq. 5). We compare the standard sparse skew-symmetric coupling of AdaDiag against an alternative sparse random coupling, where we selected randomly a number of off-diagonal blocks to match the same sparsity level of 15.6% of the skew-symmetric case. While the random topology yields uncontrolled growth of the spectral norm, the skew-symmetric structure maintains bounded dynamics throughout training. This confirms the stabilizing role of skew-symmetric coupling in the training of AdaDiag assemblies.

6. Future work

AdaDiag demonstrated promising performance, however, several aspects of its design and optimization remain open for exploration. One limitation concerns the hyperparameter C , which controls the degree of sparsity in the assembly of RNNs, has been only partially explored, as we limited our experiments to $C = 5, 20$ and 500 ; future work could investigate strategies for automatically selecting an optimal value of C for a given task. Another direction involves relaxing the assumption of a fixed connectivity graph. De-

Figure 4: Evolution of the spectral norm of the assembly block matrix during training on the Adiac dataset.

veloping mechanisms that allow to selectively switch couplings between RNN modules based on the input signal or task, further enhancing AdaDiag’s adaptability. In terms of architectural extensions, it would be interesting to explore stacks of assemblies, where RNN assemblies are organized across multiple layers to develop hierarchies of representations and multi-scale dynamics. Moreover, strategies in which individual modules are pre-trained on simpler tasks and subsequently combined to address more complex objectives could shed light on the generalization capabilities of these modular assemblies. Finally, from an applicative standpoint, evaluating AdaDiag under out-of-distribution conditions and in continual learning scenarios presents valuable directions for future research. In particular, investigating safe strategies for sequentially integrating new modules, while preserving stability and mitigating catastrophic forgetting, may open lines of research for deploying modular assemblies in dynamic real-world environments.

7. Conclusions

In this paper, we addressed the problem of constructing a stable and adaptive assembly of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). We laid the foundations of our work on the theoretical results from Kozachkov et al. (2022), where the best-performing approach proposed requires all the RNNs

of the assembly to stay *fixed* throughout the training process. Motivated by the potential benefit in the representation capabilities of the assembly by allowing the adaptivity of the modules, we proposed a strategy where the RNNs' weight matrices are parametrised as diagonal matrices to fully control their stability, and their neurons can learn their characteristic time scales to further enhance the adaptivity.

In our experiments, we systematically compared our approach with LSTM, Vanilla RNN, and the fixed baseline in Kozachkov et al. (2022), on ten time series benchmarks, considering different levels of coupling among the RNNs and, consequently, different levels of sparsity in the overall assembly. The results showed that the adaptivity of the modules leads to outperform the baseline in almost all cases. This highlighted that the inner dynamics of each RNN module benefit from adapting according to the dynamics of the others. [We also compared our results against recent deep learning architectures for time series, showing the competitiveness of our approach with the state-of-the-art.](#) In future work, we aim to generalize our approach by adapting the assembly's connectivity, selectively switching interactions between modules based on the task, and exploring sequential growth of the assembly by attaching new specialized modules during training.

Appendix A. Extended Comparison with Best-Reported Results

[Pensavo di tenere per il rebuttal questa sezione](#)

In this section, we broaden our evaluation by incorporating a diverse set of models from the recent literature and systematically compare our best-performing results with some of the strongest results reported to date. This extended comparison allows us to better situate our contribution within the wider field of time series learning, spanning classical approaches, deep learning architectures, and large-scale foundation models.

Models from the literature The pool of models considered is intentionally heterogeneous, spanning deep learning architectures (recurrent-based, convolutional-based, and attention-based), modern foundation-style approaches, and classical machine learning models. We begin with recurrent neural network baselines that are commonly referenced in the time series literature for addressing long-term dependencies. These include AntisymRNN Chang et al. (2019), a recurrent neural network variant grounded in ordinary differential equation formulations; FastGRNN Kusupati et al. (2018), SpectralRNN Zhang et al. (2018), and RoaRNN Ceni (2025), three recurrent architectures designed to improve efficiency or stability in learning long-term dependencies; and ResNet, a convolutional residual network originally developed for computer vision and later adapted to time series classification Wang et al. (2017); Ismail Fawaz et al. (2019) and regression Tan et al. (2021). Among these, AntisymRNN deserves particular attention. The antisymmetric parametrization it introduces has inspired a line of subsequent research, including SCN and our AdaDiag model, which extend this principle in a modular fashion by encouraging sparse assemblies of contractive RNN modules. AntisymRNN thus serves not only as a competitive baseline but also as a conceptual precursor, making its inclusion essential for fairly assessing whether structured extensions provide improvements over the original antisymmetric formulation.

To capture the current state of the art, we further include architectures representing distinct methodological paradigms. Convolution-based methods tailored for time series are represented by TimesNet Wu et al. (2023), Rocket Dempster et al. (2020), and InceptionTime Ismail Fawaz et al. (2020). Modern state-space models are exemplified by S4 Gu et al. (2022), designed for efficient long-sequence modeling. Transformer-based approaches appear through iTransformer Liu et al. (2024), specialized for temporal data, as well

as UniTS-SUP Gao et al. (2024) and GPT4TS Zhou et al. (2023), which reflect the growing trend of adapting large-scale language models to time series. Finally, SVR-opt Tan et al. (2021), an optimized support vector regression method, provides an advanced kernel-based baseline.

Finally, we include traditional machine learning baselines such as SVR, Random Forests, and XGBoost, providing lightweight non-neural alternatives.

Results are reported in Table A.9. We report the number of trainable parameters when available.⁴

Appendix A.1. Discussion

Table A.9: Test performance of state-of-the-art models across all datasets. Values are test accuracy (\uparrow) for classification tasks and RMSE (\downarrow) for regression tasks. Bold indicates best performance for each dataset. Results are taken from Dempster et al. (2020); Tan et al. (2021) for Rocket, ResNet, Inception, SVR-Optimised, RandomForest, XGBoost, from Gao et al. (2024) for UniTS-SUP, TimesNet, iTransformer, GPT4TS, from Kozachkov et al. (2022) for S4, Transformer, AntisymmRNN, from Kusupati et al. (2018) for FastGRNN, SpectralRNN, AntisymmRNN, and from Ceni (2025) for roaRNN. Parentheses indicate the number of trainable parameters, where such information is available.

Model	Adiac \uparrow	FordA \uparrow	FordB \uparrow	PEMS-SF \uparrow	HAR-2 \uparrow	JapVow \uparrow	PPG \downarrow	NTSent \downarrow	sMNIST \uparrow	psMNIST \uparrow
Rocket (20k)	78.34	94.44	80.51	–	–	–	36.52	0.14	–	–
ResNet (430k)	82.89	92.05	82.35	–	–	–	33.15	0.14	–	–
InceptionTime (2.2M)	83.63	94.83	93.65	–	–	–	23.90	0.16	–	–
UniTS-SUP (>1M)	–	–	–	83.20	–	92.20	–	–	–	–
TimesNet (>1M)	–	–	–	77.50	–	97.60	–	–	–	–
iTransformer (>1M)	–	–	–	83.20	–	95.90	–	–	–	–
GPT4TS (>1M)	–	–	–	79.20	–	94.60	–	–	–	–
SVR-Optimised	–	–	–	–	–	–	37.25	0.14	–	–
RandomForest	–	–	–	–	–	–	32.11	0.19	–	–
XGBoost	–	–	–	–	–	–	31.49	0.15	–	–
S4 (7.9M)	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	99.63	98.70
Transformer (0.5M)	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	98.90	97.90
RoaRNN (270k)	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	98.25
AntisymmRNN (7.5k-36k)	–	–	–	–	93.15	–	–	–	98.00	95.80
FastGRNN	–	–	–	–	95.59	–	–	–	98.20	–
SpectralRNN	–	–	–	–	95.48	–	–	–	97.70	–
AdaDiag	82.42	94.08	83.34	94.32	95.70	98.41	20.34	0.14	99.06	96.16
Tr. params (AdaDiag)	(42k)	(4.9k)	(8.7k)	(1.1M)	(13k)	(23k)	(7k)	(5.4k)	(28k)	(28k)

Table A.9 consolidates the test performance of a diverse set of models from the literature across ten benchmark datasets, covering univariate and multivariate time series, regression and classification tasks, and inputs from sensors, audio, images, and sentiment, spanning both synthetic and real-world scenarios (see Table 1 for dataset statistics). Many entries are left

⁴An estimation of the trainable parameters of ResNet and InceptionTime architectures is reported in Appendix B.

empty because not all models were originally evaluated on every dataset, yet the unified table provides a comprehensive view of performance while transparently reflecting the coverage reported in prior work.

It is important to note that our evaluation strictly separates validation and test sets: AdaDiag’s model selection is performed on a held-out validation subset, after which the best configuration is retrained on the full training data and evaluated on a strictly held-out test set, with results averaged across multiple trials. Unfortunately, not all models in Table A.9 followed this rigorous protocol, which limits direct comparability, particularly given the wide range of trainable parameters across models.

Despite these differences, AdaDiag consistently achieves top-tier performance, often matching or surpassing much larger architectures while using substantially fewer parameters. These results highlight the robustness and efficiency of AdaDiag, demonstrating that its modular, contractive design enables reliable generalization across diverse datasets and methodological paradigms.

Appendix B. Estimation of Trainable Parameters for ResNet and Inception [Double check the maths](#)

For a rigorous comparison of model complexity, we estimated the number of trainable parameters for both ResNet (Wang et al., 2017; Ismail Fawaz et al., 2019) and InceptionTime (Ismail Fawaz et al., 2020) architectures across the selected benchmark datasets. The computations considered the standard configurations reported in the literature, with three residual blocks for ResNet (filters per block: 64, 128, 128) and six Inception modules with 32 filters per module. Batch normalization and residual connections were included as in the original formulations. For InceptionTime, we considered the ensemble of five independently trained models, as suggested by Ismail Fawaz et al. (2020). Parameter counts are obtained by applying the following layer-wise formulas:

$$\#\text{Conv1D} = k \times C_{\text{in}} \times C_{\text{out}} + C_{\text{out}}, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\#\text{BatchNorm} = 2 \times C_{\text{out}}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$\#\text{Dense} = d_{\text{in}} \times d_{\text{out}} + d_{\text{out}}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where k is the kernel size, C_{in} and C_{out} are input and output channels, and $d_{\text{in}}, d_{\text{out}}$ are input and output dimensions. Global average pooling (GAP) and

residual skip connections add no parameters. A 1×1 projection convolution is included when a residual connection changes dimensionality.

Appendix B.1. Worked Example: Adiac Dataset

The Adiac dataset comprises univariate time series of length 176 with 37 classes. Following the implementation of ResNet proposed in (Wang et al., 2017; Ismail Fawaz et al., 2019), we consider three residual blocks with filters [64, 128, 128], each block containing three Conv1D layers with kernel sizes [8, 5, 3] and BatchNorm after each convolution. GAP precedes the final dense layer.

ResNet (Adiac). Table B.10 details the parameter calculation.

Table B.10: Layer-wise parameter count for ResNet on Adiac.

Layer	Computation	Parameters
Block 1 Conv1	$8 \times 1 \times 64 + 64 + 2 \times 64$	704
Block 1 Conv2	$5 \times 64 \times 64 + 64 + 2 \times 64$	20,672
Block 1 Conv3	$3 \times 64 \times 64 + 64 + 2 \times 64$	12,480
Block 2 Conv1	$8 \times 64 \times 128 + 128 + 2 \times 128$	65,920
Block 2 Conv2	$5 \times 128 \times 128 + 128 + 2 \times 128$	82,176
Block 2 Conv3	$3 \times 128 \times 128 + 128 + 2 \times 128$	49,536
Block 3 Conv1	$8 \times 128 \times 128 + 128 + 2 \times 128$	65,920
Block 3 Conv2	$5 \times 128 \times 128 + 128 + 2 \times 128$	82,176
Block 3 Conv3	$3 \times 128 \times 128 + 128 + 2 \times 128$	49,536
Dense (128 \rightarrow 37)	$128 \times 37 + 37$	4,773
Total		434,149

Thus, the ResNet architecture on Adiac contains approximately 430k trainable parameters.

InceptionTime (Adiac). For InceptionTime (Ismail Fawaz et al., 2020), each module consists of (i) an optional 1×1 bottleneck convolution reducing the input channels to $C_b = 32$, (ii) three parallel convolutions with kernel sizes {10, 20, 40} each producing 32 filters, (iii) a max-pooling branch followed by a 1×1 conv producing 32 filters, and (iv) BatchNorm after every conv.

The outputs of the four branches are concatenated, yielding 128 channels per module. Six such modules are stacked, followed by GAP and a dense layer to 37 classes. Table B.11 shows the detailed computation.

Table B.11: Parameter count for InceptionTime on Adiac (with bottleneck $C_b = 32$, branch filters $F = 32$).

Component	Computation	Parameters
Bottleneck	$1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 32 + 32 + 2 \times 32$	128
Conv branch ($k = 10$)	$10 \times 32 \times 32 + 32 + 2 \times 32$	10,336
Conv branch ($k = 20$)	$20 \times 32 \times 32 + 32 + 2 \times 32$	20,576
Conv branch ($k = 40$)	$40 \times 32 \times 32 + 32 + 2 \times 32$	41,056
Pool branch + 1×1 conv	$1 \times 32 \times 32 + 32 + 2 \times 32$	1,120
Per module total		73,216
Six modules total		439,296
Dense ($128 \rightarrow 37$)	$128 \times 37 + 37$	4,773
Single model total		444,069
5-model ensemble total		2,220,345

Hence, a single InceptionTime model contains 440k parameters, while the recommended ensemble of five independently trained models totals approximately 2.2M trainable parameters.

Appendix B.2. Extension to Other Datasets

The same procedure applies to the other datasets by adjusting the input channels in the first convolution (ResNet) or bottleneck (InceptionTime) to match the dataset, setting the output dimension of the final dense layer to the number of classes (or 1 for regression), while the sequence length does not affect parameter counts because convolutional kernels share weights along the temporal axis. This yields ≈ 430 k parameters for ResNet, and ≈ 2.2 M parameters for the five-model ensemble InceptionTime across all datasets.

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